

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Vision of Social Change in Girish Karnad's *The Fire and the Rain*

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Article History: Submitted-26/07/2025, Revised-10/08/2025, Accepted-19/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

India is a static or conventional society where caste-consciousness and religious orthodoxy are averse to any social change. The present paper seeks to examine the vision of social change in Girish Karnad's *The Fire and the Rain*. The play shows how caste-consciousness and religious orthodoxy endorsed by politics prove detrimental to the vision of an egalitarian society and hamper the possibility of social change not only in ancient times but also in the contemporary period. It reveals the fact that goodness never dwells in a particular caste or creed but in the person who is conscious of the difference between good and bad. The play illustrates how *yajna* (fire sacrifice) conducted under the royal patronage to please *Indra* to bring rain to the parched land fails because of the selfish motives of the leading priest, Parvassu while the supreme sacrifice made by the hunter girl, Nittilai pleases *Indra* to cause rain. It brings forth the view that mere knowledge or rituals without virtues of love, service and sacrifice cannot bring any social change. It is possible only through human love and the gesture of goodness as shown by innocent and kind characters like Nittilai and Arvasu.

Keywords: Orthodoxy, consciousness, detrimental, humanity, sacrificial, superiority.

Introduction

There has been a conflict between the sacred and the secular forces in all human societies throughout the world in all ages, and it has always brought in its wake death, decay and destruction. Girish Karnad's *The Fire and the Rain* dramatizes this age-old conflict through the interaction of two different castes — the Brahmins and the Hunters — in respect of customs and traditions, attitudes and behaviours, tastes and temperaments. 'The Brahmins' are symbolically represented by 'fire,' whereas 'The Hunters' are represented by 'Rain'. 'Fire' and 'Rain' have different meanings in different contexts and situations. 'Fire' has the power to destroy and engulf everything whereas 'Rain' can nurture and rejuvenate life; the former needs sacrifice whereas the latter gives birth. However, these two elements are not always only destructive or constructive in the true sense. Water in the form of flood can be destructive. On the other hand, fire has an important role to play in our lives as it witnesses every auspicious occasion from naming ceremonies to cremations and destroys evil and the unwanted. Though both fire and water are opposite in nature, they form the purest combination. It is the law of nature to balance the opposite forces. 'Fire' in the play represents power, emotions and passion; whereas 'Rain' represents sacrifice and redemption. In the Vedic tradition, "Agni, the interlocutor between the human and the divine, has always been held to be sacred and it conveys human aspirations to the higher power through *yajna*" (Nayak 48).

In ancient times, kings and wealthy persons used to organise *yajna*, the fire sacrifice to bring rain, to attain glory, sons and cattle, and to avoid death. *Yajna* is supposed to remove selfishness if performed with nurturing the feeling of total surrender. Taking fire sacrifice or the *yajna* as the central theme, the playwright presents the consequences of human actions as both enriching and troubling. In the very beginning of the play, a seven-year-long fire sacrifice is

being conducted to appease lord *Indra* to redeem the parched land from the gripping drought. It is expected that *Indra* will shower rain after the successful completion of the fire sacrifice. The prime concern of a *yajna* is to uplift man's soul, transcending human weaknesses and selfishness and pave the way for a peaceful and happy living, but the play shows its meaninglessness. *Yajna* is a kind of conversation between the human and the divine that shows aspirations of humans to reach the higher power through it. P. Jayalakshmi makes it clear that "The Vedic sacrifice, apart from the extrinsic and the material portent, is symbolic of a process in the universe that is intended to lift man's soul to the highest state of self-realization" (252).

During the Vedic age, the chief priests risked their well-being for successful completion of the *yajna* as their transgression could be harmful to the holiness of the ritual. Going away from the sacrificial precincts, indulging in a sexual relationship and talking to a low caste could have some disastrous results. However, in the play, Parvasu remains unmindful of these transgressions. He stealthily visits his hermitage to meet his wife Vishakha at night when he hears the news of her flirtation with Yavakri. This non-seriousness of the main priest towards the fire sacrifice brings an unexpected turn in the plot. It is dishonesty that defeats the very purpose of the fire sacrifice. The Brahmins use the sacrifice to be at par with the gods. In their sacrifice, their ambition reigns supreme. Through the character of Parvasu, Karnad reveals the hollow intellectuality with secretive obsession, which presents his personality in a dim light. He is the representative of all Brahmins who look serene externally but are vicious at the core of their hearts.

Brahmins think themselves to be equal to the gods but fail miserably to acquire knowledge regarding 'Brahma.' Due to his selfish quest for power to attain the stature of *Indra*, Parvasu forgets the conceptual definition of *yajna*. He is portrayed as a selfish Brahmin having

all human weaknesses like jealousy, anger and revenge. His fraternal jealousy spoils his destined goal. Even his father, Raibhya and Yavakri keep smouldering due to envy and aversion. Despite all their knowledge of scriptures, they get entangled in the web of sin because of their evil-mindedness. Raibhya is jealous of his son, Paravasu, who is chosen as the head priest by the king. However, his ambition to become the chief priest is, in a way, a proceeding towards being a victim of Bhardwaja's curse, and, in turn, is killed by his own son. Paravasu, being appointed as the leading priest of the *yajna*, serves the beginning of sins and sows the seeds of discord in the family. The power struggle jolts the lives of all the characters in the play. Yavakri, Bhardwaja's son, molests Raibhaya's daughter-in-law and has to face Raibhaya's curse in the form of his '*kritya*' Brahma *Rakshasa*, who kills Yavakri. The objective of praying to Lord *Indra* for rain is lost somewhere amidst revenge and corpses.

The play depicts the dissension and discord that arises among the learned Brahmins of the same family who scheme against one another to prove their superiority. The personal motives become more pronounced in the actions directed to achieving only their chosen selfish ends. Paravasu, Yavakri, Raibhya and Bhardwaj---all are symbolic of the negative aspects of fire which engulfs all of them. On the other hand, Arvasu and Nittilai are simple-minded, not very learned, but perform noble acts which prove to be a great sacrifice. It is to show the real motive of the myths that provide values, morals, happiness and peace that Karnad introduces the couple of Arvasu and Nittilai. By presenting the Nittilai-Arvasu relationship in contrast with the Brahmins, Karnad "blasts at the Vedic concept of brahminic superiority for their birth from Brahma's mouth and for the origin of Shudras from his feet" (Nayak 60-61). Arvasu is trapped in his caste which has just taught him anger, jealousy, enmity and knowledge but little wisdom.

As the play progresses, it becomes difficult to differentiate the godly, human and demonic behaviour of the people. Confusion prevails as it seems difficult to tell who is demon-like and who is a human being. How familial and societal relationships are manipulated to achieve personal motives is presented vehemently by the heinous acts made by the so-called learned Brahmins. After Yavakri's murder by Raibhaya, Parvasu realises that his father has killed Yavakri to disturb him lest he should complete the *yajna* successfully. He kills his father and puts the blame of patricide on his innocent brother, Arvasu, who fails to understand his crime. Parvasu's secret obsession for superiority, knowledge and power could not be subdued even by the seven years of incantation and chanting. Parvasu tries to justify his act of patricide by telling a lie to Arvasu as he explains: "In the dark, I...I mistook him for a wild animal" (Karnad 34).

Arvasu, after cremating his father, goes back to the fire sacrifice but when Parvasu looks at him, he requests the king to stop Arvasu's entry to the sanctified precincts of the sacrifice. Arvasu's protesting shouts of his innocence are heard by none. He is severely wronged by his own brother. Arvasu's repetition of 'why' with innocence and natural goodness of the human heart fails to melt the heart of Parvasu. Parvasu does not feel guilty of accusing his brother of the sin he himself has committed. He is afraid of confessing for the fear of losing his status as the chief priest and becoming an outcaste. He calls Arvasu a demon, but he himself is a demon in disguise. In fact, Parvasu, Raibhya and Yavakri are all demons in the guise of Brahmins who succumb to their materialistic pursuits and fail to transcend human weaknesses. They use their knowledge for destruction. They are after power of superiority and knowledge which makes them act in a way they do. By presenting the age-old legend in the context of the present day

world, the playwright forces the reader to sense “the dangers of knowledge without wisdom, and power without integrity” (Naik 204).

It is ironic that the Brahma rakshasa seeks liberation from the eternal darkness of immortality and takes birth in human life in the hope of getting satisfaction, but in contrast, humans like Yavakri, Parvasu and Raibhya crave for immortality and are embodiment of ‘asuric’ behaviours and harbour emotions of jealousy, lust and anger. Parvasu, Raibhya and Yavakri are not ready to accept the changes and love their static elevated status achieved by them by hook or by crook. Raibhya fails to accept Parvasu being called in by the King as the chief priest of *Yajna*. He is in conflict with his own son. As a result, Vishakha, Parvasu’s wife, becomes his prey. He tortures, humiliates and even beats her up. Vishakha tells her husband, “Something died inside your father the day the King invited you to be the Chief Priest. He’s been drying up like a dead tree since then.... On the one hand, there’s his sense of being humiliated by you. On the other, there’s lust.... An old man’s curdled lust. And there’s no one else here to take his rage out on but me” (Karnad 32-33).

The miserable life of Vishakha provides a deep insight into the patriarchal hegemony that has proved detrimental to the well-being of women for centuries. She is first loved and deserted by her lover Yavakri, then by her husband for the fire sacrifice and later abused by her father-in-law, who makes her the victim of his fire of lust and revenge. It is her long isolation in the hermitage of Raibhya that makes her submit to the advances of Yavakri and forget morality and external reality and for which she is even ready to meet her fate in death having “no concern for logic, morality...or the demands of external reality” (Budholia 152). Like a typical Indian woman, she is subjugated by male dominance, and her position is reduced to an inferior status.

Unlike Vishakha, Nittilai never loses faith in herself and dares to fight through the reversals of fortune. She is very clear about her role in life. Her role and her original self never act in opposite directions. Despite her low-caste birth, she has worldly wisdom and understanding of the virtues like love, grace, dignity and morality. Her wisdom eclipses the high-caste glory and quest for knowledge when she says: “Arvasu, when I say we should go together—I don’t mean we have to live together—like lovers or like husband and wife. I have been vicious enough to my husband. I don’t want to disgrace him further. Let’s be together—like brother and sister. You marry any girl you like. Only please, Arvasu—spare a corner for me” (Karnad 42). She has been made a spokesperson for the dramatist through whom he comments on the caste superiority and dominance, false knowledge and phoney culture of the Brahmins. She does not like the blind and orthodox behaviour of the learned class. Nittilai’s progressive and inquisitive mind interrogates secretive Brahminic practices. She poses some pertinent questions while comparing the rituals performed by Brahmins to those of hunters:

But what I want to know is why are the Brahmins so secretive about everything?
(*Continuing.*) You know, their fire sacrifices are conducted in covered enclosures. They mortify themselves in the dark of the jungle. Even their gods appear so secretly. Why? What are they afraid of? Look at my people. Everything is in public view there. The priest announces that he’ll invoke the deity at such and such a time on such and such day. And then there, right in front of the whole tribe, he gets possessed. And the spirit answers your questions. You can feel it come and go. You *know* it’s there. Not mere hearsay ---.
(Karnad 10)

Apart from presenting the conflict between bookish knowledge and simple emotions, the play also brings forth what is projected as right by the so-called learners of *Vedas*. In fact, they

camouflage their inner impure selves. Parvasu kills his father and blames Arvasu, who is believed to be a murderer and is thrown out of the sacrificial site. The modern man has a tendency to compromise with human ethics and lacks morality in his deeds. He has a sense of false superiority which makes him believe that he is above everyone and everything. But in reality he has lost faith in himself and just puts a pose before others. That is why the desired result of the fire sacrifice is not achieved. All the learned characters in the play employ their intelligence to further their end. They lack the capability to think beyond themselves. For Parvasu, the *yajna* is just a formal structured ritual which is used by him to assert his superiority over others. Such futile ambitions result in the loss of human qualities. That is why the fire sacrifice fails. Nittilai shows her faith in change and appreciates Arvasu for playing the part of a demon. She is of the view that those who do not have a fear of death cannot enjoy life. Life loses its meaning without the idea of change. She does not like *Indra* for his immortality. Rightly, she puts it thus:

Nittilai: I'm glad you're not playing Indra. I don't like that god of yours.

Arvasu: Why?

Nittilai: He is immortal. When someone doesn't die, can't die, what can he know about anything? He can't change himself. He can't — Can't *create* anything. I like Vritra because even when he's triumphant he chooses death. I always wonder—if the flowers didn't know they were to fade and die, would they have ever blossomed? (Karnad 51)

It is only through the selfless and benign Nittilai and generous Arvasu that the playwright seeks relief for the parched land. Nittilai shows the true meaning of learning, sacrifice and penance. She knows that knowledge means control of passions. Both Nittilai and Arvasu are

symbolic of water that nurtures life. Their plainness and kindness combined with pure intentions create the power to redeem the cursed land. The Brahmins make use of their magical powers to destroy, whereas Arvasu, though a Brahmin, makes use of his talent as an actor for entertaining others and for the betterment of all. By dramatizing “the mythological episode of Arvasu’s love for a tribal girl of hunting community, Karnad very significantly condemns and ridicules the caste system which has been social stigma for ages” (Kumar 179). Parvasu performs the fire sacrifice just for the sake of it and has personal desires behind it; whereas Arvasu makes the sacrifice without any selfish motive. Arvasu’s triumph over others and even *Indra* proves the power of the empirical approach towards sacrifice. Moreover, the triumph of Arvasu is the triumph of the power of drama. It is only because of the power of the play that Arvasu is able to impress *Indra* with his noble acts.

It is the magic of the play that we find a glimpse of social change, as the play is open to all the upper class and the lower class people who were debarred from entering the sacrificial precincts. *Indra* is impressed by the acting of Arvasu, who as *Vritra* poses a challenge to *Indra*. The god, pleased by the acting of Arvasu, asks him to make a single wish: “We (the gods) loved the way you challenged *Indra* and then pursued him in the play. But it could also be because of Parvasu’s sacrifice or *Nittilai*’s humanity. You humans are free to construe the acts of gods as you wish. The point is we are here and you can ask for anything you want—” (Karnad 59). In grief and sigh of relief, Arvasu wants *Nittilai* to come alive, but the crowd wants him to ask for rain. They shout, “Rain! Arvasu, ask for the rains! Water—” (59). But not listening to what the crowd is saying, he wishes, “Lord *Indra*, I want *Nittilai* back. Alive. That’s all I want in my life. Grant me that. *Nittilai*—my gentle *Nittilai*—I killed her. I want her back—” (59).

However, Lord *Indra* tries to make Arvasu understand that bringing Nittilai back to life is not a big thing for the gods and he should think beyond himself for greater good. At this moment Brahma Rakshasa appears and asks for his release from the eternal hell of immortality. He begs Arvasu, "I want release—release from this bondage. Your father gave me this life. We are brothers. So you must complete what your father couldn't—I want to melt away—I want peace—eternal peace—I beg of you—intercede on my behalf with the gods—" (60). Arvasu realises that if Nittilai had been alive, she would also have made the same decision. So, he asks for Brahmaraakshasa's release, and at this moment rain falls in abundance and mercy triumphs. Arvasu goes beyond his individual ego and understands the perceptions of *Indra* and realises: "I'm wiser. I can now stop the tragedy from repeating itself" (65). Arvasu's sacrifice is the true sacrifice, as Rama Nair says: "True sacrifice is that of love, especially that which is for the benefit of humanity. It cleanses as and purifies, like gentle rain, the 'fallen' state of this world" (248).

Conclusion

Through the play Karnad presents the age-old societal attitude towards women, actors, lovers and low castes. The central action of the play revolves around love, betrayal, ambition, revenge, futility and sacrifice, thereby presenting the frailty of human nature and the evil residing therein. Evil is natural in every human being, and it destroys everything. The fire of jealousy intoxicates the human mind and ruins it. Raibhya's jealousy for his son and Yavakri's penance out of jealousy show the degree of moral upliftment of the learned class. What Karnad wants to convey is that morality never dwells in a particular class or creed, but in the person who is conscious of the distinction between moral and amoral. Though Arvasu is a high-caste Brahmin, he is taught by a tribal girl, Nittilai, the real meaning of virtue. The one who shuns casteism and other

bondages and becomes an embodiment of humanism, is able to overcome the conflicts in one's life is the most successful man, whether he belongs to a high class or the low caste. Superficial knowledge of hymns or *Vedas* does not necessarily uplift a human soul, but the love for humanity can help in uplifting the society. The 'Rain' which is symbolic of milk of human kindness showers only after Arvasu's and Nittilai's sacrifice. They sacrifice the particular for the general that evokes the spirit of humanism. The play also brings to the fore the fact that gods are not impressed by sacrifice of any kind or penance that Yavakri follows, but by innocence, kindness, truthfulness and loyalty. True sacrifices are control of passions and transcendence of all that is material. Karnad provides the possibility of social change through the characters of Nittilai and Arvasu, who have the potential to relieve the famine-stricken masses of starvation and death. It also brings forth the view that mere knowledge or rituals without the virtues of love, service and sacrifice cannot bring about any social change.

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